

Deliverable 5.4.1.1

ARCHITECTURE AND INTERFACE DEFINITION OF THE
SIMULATION-AS-A-SERVICE HUB FOR CO-SIMULATION
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Architecture and Interface Definition of the Simulation-as-a-Service Hub for Co-Simulation

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General information

Summary

Task Area 5 of the NFDI4Energy consortium is developing a Simulation-as-a-Service (SimaaS) hub that provides energy researchers with flexible, interactive, and scalable simulation solutions. The aim is to make complex simulation tools accessible via a standardized infrastructure and to integrate their use into the NFDI4Energy service landscape.

Measure 5.4 focuses on the technical and conceptual integration of the services developed in Task Area 5 into the overall service landscape. This requires a well-defined architecture that describes the relationships between front-end and back-end components and specifies the interfaces of the individual services.

This document provides a structured overview of the planned architecture of the SimaaS hub within the NFDI4Energy service landscape and describes the prototypical implementation of the SimaaS API.

Deliverable 5.4.1.1 within NFDI4Energy

Task Area 5 aims to advance interdisciplinary simulation approaches in energy systems research. To this end, two central services are being developed for the NFDI4Energy service landscape:

- a software registry for describing and managing simulation tools,
- and a SimaaS for executing simulations.

Measure 5.4 focuses on integrating these two services into the NFDI4Energy service landscape. Deliverable 5.4.1.1 outlines the planned integration approach and explains how the services can be accessed.

Deliverable description

Introduction

Within the NFDI4Energy consortium, we are developing a Simulation-as-a-Service (SimaaS) hub to support energy researchers in the use of simulation-based methods [1]. While SimaaS provides simplified, standardized, and scalable access to simulation frameworks, our analysis of domain-specific use cases has shown that access alone is not sufficient.

Researchers also require support in selecting appropriate simulation tools, understanding their usage, and creating suitable simulation scenarios. To address these needs, the SimaaS approach is extended into a broader SimaaS hub that combines technical infrastructure with supporting services.

The hub therefore provides an interoperable environment that integrates simulation services, software discovery via a registry, and mechanisms for managing and reusing simulation scenarios. This holistic approach aims to reduce technical barriers, facilitate the learning and application of simulation tools, and improve the reproducibility and comparability of simulation studies in the energy domain.

The SimaaS hub builds on two central technical components:

- **Simulation-as-a-Service:** The SimaaS integrates several co-simulation frameworks and provides their functionalities via a uniform programming interface (API). The following frameworks will be supported: mosaik [2], DaceDSX [3], and VILLASframework [4].
- **Software Registry:** The software registry is used to manage, describe, and locate available simulation tools and software artifacts.

We plan to use an existing registry solution that already provides a standardized API. In the context of NFDI4Energy, we will extend the registry with a domain-specific metadata schema (ERSMeta¹) to map domain-specific requirements [5]. Therefore, we will not develop a new API for the registry. Instead, the existing interface will be extended and adapted.

We have implemented our own API for the SimaaS. Our implementation is conceptually based on the API of the OpenPlan tool's simulation-server² and extends it with domain-specific functionalities for orchestrating, managing, and monitoring co-simulations. OpenPlan³ is a web-based platform for configuring and performing energy system simulations using the oemof framework.

This document aims to provide a structured overview of the SimaaS hub architecture and to describe the prototypical implementation of the provided SimaaS API. Since both—the API implementation and the underlying infrastructure—may change, this document focuses on the conceptual structure and defined interfaces. Implementation details are deliberately presented in abstract form only. The current status and implementation can be found on GitHub⁴.

SimaaS Architecture

The architecture of the SimaaS hub follows a three-layer model as shown in Figure 1. It separates everything into the infrastructure, communication, and service layer. This structure aims to clearly separate responsibilities in order to ensure the modularity, expandability, and maintainability of the system.

Infrastructure Layer

The infrastructure layer provides the technical foundation for the SimaaS hub. It provides all runtime, storage, and orchestration components required for the execution and management of simulations.

¹<https://github.com/NFDI4Energy/ERSmeta>

²<https://github.com/open-plan-tool/simulation-server>

³<https://open-plan-tool.org/en/>

⁴<https://github.com/NFDI4Energy/nfdi4energy-simulation-server>

Service	NFDI4Energy Platform Frontend			
	User Management			
	Scenario Management			
Communication	Scenario Ontology			ERSMeta
	Simulation-Server-API			Software Registry API
Infrastructure	Simulation-Server-Tasks			Software Registry
	DaceDSX-Container	mosaik-Container	VILLASframework - Container	

Figure 1: Architecture overview of SimaaS hub

The infrastructure layer includes:

- the software registry database,
- containerization and orchestration technologies,
- container with the integrated co-simulation frameworks (mosaik, DaceDSX, VILLASframework),
- management components.

To avoid interference between the individual simulation frameworks, each will run in its own container. We use Docker for containerization and Kubernetes [6] for orchestration, scaling, and resource management.

OpenPlan provides a simulation server that we have further developed into a generalized simulation server. Instead of being directly linked to a specific simulation tool, it forwards incoming API requests and associated input files to registered workers via a message queue. The queue enables loose coupling between the API and simulation frameworks.

The actual simulation execution takes place in isolated, temporary Kubernetes jobs. These are dynamically scheduled and executed. This decoupling keeps task management independent of the underlying hardware infrastructure, enabling a later transition from a local environment to a distributed cluster architecture without modifying the application codebase.

Communication Layer

The communication layer represents the defined interface between the front end, external services, and the internal system logic. It encapsulates the backend implementation and enables standardized interaction with the provided services.

An existing solution that already provides a standardized API will be used for the software registry. We will extend this API in the NFDI4Energy context to include the ERSMeta metadata schema. External services can access metadata and registered software artifacts via the registry API.

The API of the SimaaS was implemented independently and is based on the Python framework FastAPI [7]. It provides a RESTful-compliant HTTP API and acts as a central access level for simulation jobs, status queries, and result downloads. The format of the scenario files will be compliant with the scenario ontology [8]. In the section "Simulation-Server-API" we provide more detail on the structure of this API.

Service Layer

The application layer forms the functional level of the SimaaS hub. It comprises all components required for user interaction and for managing simulations and software artifacts.

This layer includes:

- the front end,
- user management,
- scenario management.

Frontend The frontend is the central interface for user interaction. It enables the configuration and execution of simulations as well as the addition, editing, and searching of entries in the software registry. A mock up of the frontend is described in [1].

User Management User management ensures that artifacts, simulation results, and registry entries are assigned to individual users. This allows resources to be clearly managed and edited later if necessary.

Scenario Management Scenario management stores simulation configurations and enables their reuse and sharing. By ensuring consistent simulation reproducibility, this component significantly enhances scientific reproducibility.

The application layer thus links user interaction with the underlying service and infrastructure components and provides a consistent, user-oriented service environment.

Simulation-Server-API

The simulation-server-API serves as the external service interface for the SimaaS hub. It is part of the communication layer and enables external clients to access the simulation infrastructure.

The API is implemented as a REST-compliant HTTP service and uses JSON as its primary data format. Simulation jobs are processed asynchronously via a message queue-based worker architecture.

Architectural Context

The API performs the following core functions:

- Acceptance and validation of simulation requests,
- Management of the simulation job lifecycle,
- Provision of status information,
- Provision of simulation results.

Asynchronous processing ensures that the API service remains responsive even under high load.

Communication parameters

- Protocol: HTTP
- Architecture style: REST
- Data format: JSON
- File transfer: multipart/form-data

Endpoints

The API provides the following endpoints:

- **GET /** – Provides the prototype's home page.
- **POST /submit** – Submits a new simulation including input files; returns a task ID.
- **GET /check/{task_id}** – Query the current status of a simulation job.
- **GET /list_files/{task_id}** – List the generated result files.
- **GET /download/{task_id}/{filename}** – Download a specific result file.

Status management includes the states PENDING, RUNNING, DONE, ERROR, and NOT_FOUND. Incorrect or unknown task IDs result in an HTTP 404 response.

Conclusion and next steps

This document describes the conceptual architecture of the SimaaS hub and the prototypical implementation of the associated API. It presents the three-layer system architecture comprising the infrastructure, communication, and application layers, the integration of multiple co-simulation frameworks, and RESTful APIs serving as the central access interface for external services.

In the next steps, we will extend the API to validate the content of submitted scenario files and provide feedback on format conformity. To this end, a common scenario definition is currently being developed based on the scenario ontology [8], which will serve as a structural basis for simulation configurations.

In parallel, we implement a prototype of the infrastructure layer that fully maps container-based orchestration and is closely linked to the existing API. Once this implementation is complete, deployment to suitable server infrastructures will take place. In addition, a production-ready front end is planned to support user-oriented interaction with the SimaaS hub.

All implementations will be made available on GitHub⁵, where they will be continuously updated and documented in technical detail.

⁵<https://github.com/NFDI4Energy>

References

- [1] C. Seiwert et al., "Towards a simulation-as-a-service hub for the energy domain," Mar. 25, 2025, Conference Name: 2. NFDI4Energy Conference Publisher: Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17431852. Accessed: Nov. 27, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/17431852>.
- [2] C. Steinbrink et al., "CPES testing with mosaik: Co-simulation planning, execution and analysis," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 5, 2019, ISSN: 2076-3417. DOI: 10.3390/app9050923. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/9/5/923>.
- [3] C. Seiwert, N. Halikulov, and R. German, *D 5.3.3.1 extending a data-centric distributed simulation framework for the energy domain*, Apr. 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15268434. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268434>.
- [4] S. Vogel, N. Eiling, M. Pitz, A. Bach, M. Stevic, and P. A. Monti, "Villasnode: An open-source real-time multi-protocol gateway," *Journal of Open Source Software*, vol. 10, no. 112, p. 8401, 2025. DOI: 10.21105/joss.08401. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.08401>.
- [5] S. Ferenz, O. Werth, and A. Nieße, *Towards a metadata schema for energy research software*, 2026. arXiv: 2601.09456 [cs.SE]. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2601.09456>.
- [6] E. A. Brewer, "Kubernetes and the path to cloud native," in *Proceedings of the Sixth ACM Symposium on Cloud Computing*, ser. SoCC '15, Kohala Coast, Hawaii: Association for Computing Machinery, 2015, p. 167, ISBN: 9781450336512. DOI: 10.1145/2806777.2809955. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2806777.2809955>.
- [7] S. Ramírez, *FastAPI*, original-date: 2018-12-08T08:21:47Z, Nov. 27, 2025. Accessed: Nov. 27, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/fastapi/fastapi>.
- [8] J. S. Schwarz, P. Schmurr, C. Seiwert, Z. Pan, and R. Qussous, "Adapted ontology development process: A co-simulation scenario ontology for energy systems," in *3. NFDI4Energy Conference*, in publication process, Aachen, Germany: IEEE, Mar. 2026.